

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

MAPPING OF THE “E-METHANOL AS FUEL FOR VESSELS” VALUE CHAIN

Deliverable D2.2

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CHANGE CONTROL

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the collaborative work done in the project's 6 first months to define the “e-methanol as fuel for vessels” value chain.

This preliminary work is of great importance for the project as it defines, the boundaries of the value chain that will be considered by all the deliverables of the project and ensures a common frame for the different analysis that will be done.

It was also the opportunity for the consortium partners to have their first content-oriented workshops where everybody had the opportunity to share their vision of the project and confront this vision with the other partners.

The work done in this report has also been used to communicate about the project (consortium meeting, Advisory board meeting, COP meeting in Valencia) and will be used in the frame of D.7.2 (promotional toolkit and website) to present the value chain of the project.

The document features 4 main chapters:

- Methodology used to generate the results => Chapter 2;
- Presentation of the considered value chain => Chapter 3;
- Main key players => Chapter 4;
- Use of the value chain in the project => Chapter 5.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
AVEBIOM	Asociacion Espanola de la Valorizacion Energetica de la Biomasa
CERTH	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
COP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EDF	Electricite de France
EIFER	Europäisches Institut für Energieforschung EDF-KIT EWIV
FC	Fincantieri SPA
FVP	Fundacion de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Investigacion, Promocion y Estudios Comerciales de Valenciaport
GOMSL	Global Omnium Medioambiente, S.L
ICODOS	ICODOS GmbH
IFM	Isotta Fraschini Motori S.P.A.
INV	Inventors SA
KIT	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life cycle costing
MDO	Marine Diesel Oil
RCF	Recycled carbon fuels
RINA	RINA Consulting SPA
RFNBO	Renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin
S-LCA	Social Impact Assessment
SMA	Swedish Maritime Administration

STEINBEIS	Steinbeis Innovation GgmbH
STEMS	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
T	Task
TEA	Techno-Economic Analysis
ThPA	Organismos Limenos Thessalonikis Anonymi Etairia
VCH	Value chain
WinGD	Winterthur Gas & Diesel AG
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable summarizes the work done in the frame of the task T2.1 on the “Mapping of the value chain and of the key stakeholders”. The goal of the POSEIDON project is to investigate the use of synthetic methanol as fuel to support the decarbonization of the maritime sector. One of the main specificities of the project is that, in addition of investigating the different technological bricks necessary to produce, distribute and use this fuel, POSEIDON will create a consolidated vision of the whole value chain from resources (H₂, CO₂) providers to end users of the fuel (ship operators).

Since the project scope spans over several value chain steps, it is very important to define quite precisely at the beginning of the project the boundaries of the considered value chain. The objective of this deliverable is to develop a common vision for all the partners of the “e-methanol as fuel for vessel”. This ensures a global frame for all the project and deliverables, ensuring coherent approaches, scope and results.

This work has also been a good opportunity to start the project with collaborative activities in order to allow to all partners to share their view on the project’s objectives and the value chain and to confront their vision with the other partners. As POSEIDON consortium is quite large and diverse (CO₂ producers/providers, electricity providers, synthetic methanol producer, ports, vessel/engine manufacturers, maritime authorities, research centers...), all the partners provided valuable information which put together led to the value chain to be investigated in the project.

This report will first present the methodology developed by partner Steinbeis to have a collaborative definition of the value chain and make the link with some other activities of the project like the COP development. We will then present the different steps of the value chain considered in POSEIDON, including the technological steps that will need to be investigated in the different activities and deliverables of the project. The key stakeholders composing the value chain and their relationships are presented in a third part, paving the way for the local work in Valencia and Thessaloniki for the development of the local COPs. The last part of the report presents how the work done in T2.1 will feed the rest of the project tasks and WPs.

2 METHODOLOGY

The approach followed to develop an “e-methanol as fuel for shipping” value chain relies on a series of workshops conducted between October 2023 and March 2024 (see Figure 1). Prior to the first workshop, a first version of the value chain was developed by partners EIFER and Steinbeis and presented during the kick-off meeting in Karlsruhe in September 2023. Then one month later, the first online workshop took place and focused on the fine-tuning of the technical bricks composing the value chain as well as the identification of information providers among project partners. In January 2024, three separate workshops took place: two focusing on the characterization of the value chains of the two case studies of Valencia and Thessaloniki respectively and a third one dedicated to the description of the fuel end-use onboard ships. The latter allowed to map the technical ship configurations to be further explored and to identify suitable ship types for e-methanol use. A last workshop was organized in the framework of the second partners meeting in Valencia in March 2024 and was crucial to get feedback from the members of the advisory board and align all viewpoints and officially close the value chain mapping activity.

Figure 1: Methodology consisting of a series of workshop followed within POSEIDON to develop the value chain

2.1 FIRST STAGE: GENERAL WORKSHOP WITH ALL PARTNERS OF THE CONSORTIUM

A first workshop took place on October 11th, 2023. It followed a first presentation of the value chain during the kick-off meeting held in Karlsruhe in early September 2023 that allowed to collect first feedback. This online workshop which lasted 90 minutes consisted of three main exercises:

1. Partners had to provide feedback and check that all important bricks of the value chain required to model various scenarios are represented,
2. Partners had to indicate if they can provide technical information regarding the following: 1. Stakeholders involved at the different value chain steps, 2. Technical solutions to consider for each of the value chain brick, 3. Data to be used for modelling purposes,

- Partners had to state which technical options should be investigated when assessing the two use cases of POSEIDON in Valencia and Thessaloniki.

The workshop was moderated by partners EIFER and Steinbeis. The first exercise was conducted as a general discussion and feedback round while the other exercises were done using the ideation and visualization tool Mural. The templates (whiteboard with empty tables, see Figure 2) were developed by Steinbeis prior to the workshop and attendees could add their inputs by pinning virtual sticky notes when logged in the Mural tool.

Technological brick - Feedstock	I can provide information regarding 1. stakeholders involved, 2. technical solutions available, 3 data	Technical options to be investigated within POSEIDON
Electricity mix		
Hydrogen production		
CO2 source		
CO2 capture and storage		
Biomass source		
Biogas production		
Biogas upgrade		
Bio-methane management		
CO2 purification		

Figure 2. Template “Technological brick – Feedstock” used to collect information for the 2nd and 3rd exercises of the first workshop on value chain mapping.

Results helped to improve the value chain mapping and the second version of the value chain served as input for the second stage workshops focusing on the use cases (see next section).

2.2 SECOND STAGE: FOCUS ON THE SPANISH AND GREEK CASE STUDIES

The second stage workshops were dedicated to the characterization of the two uses cases in Valencia and Thessaloniki. These workshops were moderated by community of practice (COP) managers ThPA and FVP using materials developed by partner Steinbeis. In December 2023, a coordination meeting involving partners EIFER, Steinbeis, ThPA and FVP took place to present the concept of these workshops and share guidelines on how to best conduct the exercises with the workshop participants.

Later in January 2024, COP community managers held two separate workshops: FVP had a workshop with Spanish project partners and stakeholders from Valencia while ThPA had one with Greek project partners and stakeholders from Thessaloniki. During these workshops, COP managers ThPA and FVP introduced the POSEIDON project, presented the COP concept and the second version of the value chain mapping as a result of the 1st workshop. Then 2 exercises were performed: a first exercise dedicated to the detailed description of the technical options to be

explored within POSEIDON for the considered use case and a second one focusing on the identification and mapping of local stakeholders as well as the definition of the essential characteristics of a successful COP in Valencia and Thessaloniki (results of exercise on COP are presented in more detail in deliverable D2.1 on COP framework).

Figure 3: Results collected during the second workshop focusing on the Spanish use case of Valencia.

After the workshops took place, a wrap-up meeting was held between the COP community managers and partners EIFER and Steinbeis to discuss the results and see how to modify the value chain mapping and prepare the next steps.

2.3 THIRD STAGE: FOCUS ON THE END USE PART OF THE VALUE CHAIN (ENGINES AND SHIPS)

In January 2024, partners Steinbeis and EIFER invited POSEIDON partners, IFM, WinGD and FC to a third workshop focusing on the end-use stage of the value chain which corresponds to the use of e-methanol as fuel onboard ships. This workshop was organized as an open discussion round. Partners Steinbeis and EIFER presented the technical layout of two configurations (1. engine only, 2. both engine and fuel cell) for the propulsion and energy system of the ship to be investigated, and feedback was given by engines manufacturer WinGD and IFM as well as ship builder FC.

WinGD (Bartosz)

Ship types: tugboat, ferry, cruise vessel, container vessel e.g. feeder or what visits Valencia and Thessaloniki, other 2stroke vessel such as bulker, small tanker etc. (need to be aligned with vessels that typically call at Thessaloniki and Valencia)

Data: can offer data on performance or fuel consumption and emissions of our engines. We can also see if we can get some vessel profiles

Open question: Should we consider for some vessels also residual fuel?

FC (Marco)

Ship types: Ferries (Fincantieri market), Cruises (Fincantieri primary market), Containers

Data: size, performance, power onboard installed, primary system onboard, indicative daily consumption

Figure 4. Examples of feedback collected during the third stage workshop.

This workshop allowed to bring views of partners closer together, to identify the essential technology bricks related to fuel end use to represent in the value chain and to determine the ship types to consider for both case studies.

2.4 FOURTH AND FINAL STAGE: PRESENTATION TO PROJECT PARTNERS AND ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS IN VALENCIA IN MARCH 2024

On March 5th and 6th, three sessions of the second partners meeting hosted in Valencia dealt with the POSEIDON value chain: a WP2 workshop involving only project partners, a meeting with members of the advisory board and a first in-person meeting with local COP members of Valencia. These meetings and associated discussions allowed to address last open questions and get feedback from partners external to the project. This final review exercise of the POSEIDON value chain led to the final version of the “e-methanol as fuel for shipping” value chain which is described in more depth in the next chapter.

Figure 5: Discussions on the project and POSEIDON value chain during the 2nd partner meeting in Valencia in March 2024

3 THE “SYNTHETIC METHANOL AS FUEL FOR SHIPPING” VALUE CHAIN

Following the workshops, the value chain has been split in 4 main consecutive steps:

- Main resources needed;
- Methanol production;
- Transport, logistics to the port and bunkering;
- Onboard operations.

Each of these steps are presented in the following sections and decomposed in individual technological bricks. In this report, the bricks of the value chain are presented in a generic way (with no technical / economical details) in order to define the value chain and the role of the different bricks. The detailed description of these bricks, including related data to be considered, will be done in following deliverables of the project:

- D2.4 – Summary about the state of the art of the technologies (due M18);
- D2.6 – Model description of the technologies (due M20);
- D2.8 – Technological Databases for the case studies and tool development (due M21).

3.1 MAIN RESOURCES NEEDED

In order to evaluate the resources needed for methanol production, we can consider the following equation describing the chemical reaction (direct methanolation):

Hence, two main resources need to be considered in the description of the value chain:

- Hydrogen;
- Carbon Dioxide.

A simplified scheme of the methanol synthesis is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Generic “Feedstock” value chain considered in POSEIDON.

Both molecules are not naturally available in a form and quality that could be used for the methanol synthesis. The different technologies needed to produce (e.g. hydrogen) and/or capture (e.g. carbon dioxide) needs to be included in the value chain description.

3.1.1 HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

As hydrogen (in molecular form) is not naturally present¹, it needs to be produced from other sources:

- Conversion of fossil fuels (methane reforming...);
- Water Electrolysis using different electricity mixes;
- Conversion of non-fossil materials (biomass, wastes...).

As illustrated in Figure 7, these different production pathways of hydrogen are usually referred to as a color of the hydrogen.

Figure 7: Hydrogen production pathways and associated colors (Broadleaf, 2021)

In order to produce RNFBOs, Renewable hydrogen needs to be used according to the first delegated act of the EU Commission².

POSEIDON will therefore focus on green hydrogen produced by water electrolysis powered with renewable electricity. The primary resources to be considered in the value chain will then be:

- Water;
- Renewable Electricity.

¹ Recent publications show the presence of “Native hydrogen” (also named “white hydrogen”) in some regions. However, this resource is in its first development stage and its use for industrial applications is still uncertain. We therefore decided not to consider Native hydrogen in the POSEIDON’s value chain.

² [EU Delegated Acts on Renewable Hydrogen \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L0218)

Remark: Hydrogen produced through the thermochemical conversion of biomass and/or wastes is considered as “green hydrogen”. However, biomass and wastes could be directly thermochemically converted to fuels like bio-methanol. This direct conversion to fuel would have a much lower cost and higher energetic efficiency than converting the biomass/wastes resources to green hydrogen and subsequently combining it with captured CO₂ to produce methanol. The conversion of these resources into hydrogen have therefore not been considered as relevant for the POSEIDON value chain.

3.1.2 CARBON DIOXIDE SOURCES

Carbon dioxide can be captured from different sources:

- Fossil fuel-based energy production systems (boiler, power plant...);
- Industrial processes (cement, lime...);
- Biomass/ wastes conversion units (combustion, fermentation, thermo-chemical treatments...);
- From air (DAC - Direct Air Capture).

POSEIDON's value chain will consider all CO₂ sources except the fossil-based ones, as synthetic fuels produced with fossil CO₂ would not be considered in the future as a renewable / low carbon fuel. According to the RED II delegated act of the EU Commission, the origin of carbon used to produce renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO) and recycled carbon fuels (RCF) will be restricted starting from 2036 for emissions from non-sustainable fuels and from 2041 for industrial processes. Industrial CO₂ emitted by lime production will therefore be not considered as eligible for RFNBO production in the upcoming future. We however chose to dedicate the POSEIDON's case study of Thessaloniki to the production of synthetic methanol from industrial CO₂ as these sources are not avoidable, long lasting and regionally available. The question of their use for synthetic fuels production (vs CCS) is interesting to be considered.

3.1.3 MAIN TECHNOLOGICAL BRICKS CONSIDERED

3.1.3.1 ELECTRICITY SUPPLY

To assess the situation in various European countries, different electricity mixes will be considered in the project, in order to be able to evaluate the impacts of these mixes on the whole value chain (carbon content, costs...). The following supply scenarios will be considered in the project:

- National electricity mixes from EU countries
- Electricity supply from dedicated renewable sources
- Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) with different contents
 - o 100% renewable electricity,
 - o x% renewable + grid baseload.

Electricity will be needed all along the value chain to power the different technologies. Most of the electricity demand will be needed to power the electrolyzers producing green hydrogen.

3.1.3.2 ELECTRICITY STORAGE SYSTEMS

To directly connect renewable, fluctuating energy sources, such as wind or solar-based electricity generation, and provide stability for continuous and stable operation of elements of the e-methanol value chain (mainly methanol synthesis reactors employing catalysts and operating with minimum required load – both of which are highly sensitive to operational fluctuations), energy storage systems should be considered. Sudden shutdowns or frequent load variations can negatively impact reactor performance, reduce catalyst efficiency, and accelerate catalyst deactivation due to thermal stress, coking, or sintering.

In the next stages of the project different types of battery energy storage systems (lithium-ion, sodium-ion, solid-state, redox...) will be considered and integrated into the overall system as needed for each specific case.

3.1.3.3 WATER SUPPLY

To be able to consider different implementation situations of the value chain, a large pool of raw water sources will be considered in the value chain evaluation:

- Tap water
- Ground water
- Output water of a WWTP
- Recycling of Methanol wastewater
- Sea water

Each of these raw water sources will be described and available in the tool, in terms of quality and average composition in order to be able to define the treatment steps necessary to bring them to the required quality for an electrolyser.

3.1.3.4 WATER TREATMENT

Hydrogen production via water electrolysis requires the use of ultra-pure water with no impurities and a very low conductivity (average value $< 1\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, but it depends on the electrolysis technology). Different combination and configuration of technologies will be needed to treat the different types of raw water considered in the previous paragraph into ultra-pure water.

The non-exhaustive list of the technologies that will be considered includes:

- Seawater desalination
- Filtration (physical, membrane, adsorptive, advanced and hybrid...)
- Deionisation (ion exchange, reverse osmosis...)
- Chemical treatments (flocculation / coagulation/ clarification...)
- Sedimentation

3.1.3.5 WATER ELECTROLYSIS

Different technologies of water electrolysis are currently available on the market, with different technical characteristics, maturity, related costs... As part of POSEIDON project, we will consider the technologies that are currently available on the market or that are planned to enter the market in the next years:

- Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzers;
- Alkaline electrolyzers;
- Solid Oxide Cell (SOC) electrolyzers.

This step shall also consider all the hydrogen conditioning steps necessary for its further use in the value chain (drying, compression...).

3.1.3.6 H₂ STORAGE

Depending on specific case scenario, hydrogen produced for e-methanol synthesis may require on-site storage for buffering purposes (if both processes occur in the same location) or storage for transport purposes to separate e-methanol plant. The main advanced technologies stored hydrogen (gaseous, liquid and solid), through two main storage methods: physical storage (via compression or liquefaction) and material-based storage (through chemical bonding or absorption in solid materials). High-pressure gaseous hydrogen storage (typically exceeding 300 bars) is a well-established and widely used technology. On the other hand, liquid hydrogen stored in cryogenic temperatures (~-253°C) offers a significantly higher volumetric energy density, making it more space-efficient option.

3.1.3.7 H₂ TRANSPORT

In case of hydrogen production taking place in a different location than the methanol synthesis facility, it is then needed to include the hydrogen transportation.

For H₂ transportation, compressed hydrogen gas is stored in specially designed, high-pressure tanks, typically made from steel with carbon coatings or lightweight composites to ensure safety and efficiency. For road transport, horizontal tubular tanks are preferred due to their stability and ease of handling, while spherical tanks are favored for maritime transport. Although cryogenic hydrogen tanks are lighter than pressurized tanks, their insulated storage systems are complex and present maintenance challenges. For the purpose of the POSEIDON project, long distance maritime hydrogen transport will not be analyzed.

3.1.3.8 CO₂ CAPTURE

CO₂ capture technologies have to be adapted to the targeted CO₂ source, mainly regarding CO₂ concentration in the off gas, the presence of pollutants and the quantity / flow to capture. The following families of technologies will be considered:

- Absorption technologies (physical and chemical solvents...);
- Membrane technologies;
- Cryogenic technologies.

3.1.3.9 CO₂ PURIFICATION

Depending on the implemented technology, CO₂ coming from the capture unit might not have the required quality to be directly used in the methanol synthesis reactor. In fact, fuel synthesis processes are catalytical processes which are quite sensitive to the quality of the input components. The specifications for input gases of methanol production are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Gas purity requirements for Cu/ZnO methanol catalyst (Dietrich, Buttler, Hanel, Spliethoff, & Fendt, 2020)

Syngas component	Purity requirement
H ₂ S	< 0,05 – 0,5 ppm
HCl	1 ppb
Metal carbonyl	Few ppb
Particles	< 0,1 mg N m ⁻³
Tar	< 1,0 mg N m ⁻³
Alkalis	< 0,25 mg N m ⁻³

Some intermediate purification steps might then be necessary to bring the CO₂ flow to the required quality. The CO₂ purification stage shall also consider all the CO₂ conditioning steps necessary for its further use in the value chain (drying, compression...).

3.1.3.10 CO₂ STORAGE

Depending on specific case scenario, after CO₂ is captured, separated and purified, the gas stream can be converted to e-methanol either directly at the capture-site or transported to a separate production facility. In both cases, storage might be included within the value chain, either as a buffer, to ensure continuous production or for transportation purposes.

CO₂ can be stored in two primary physical states: gaseous and liquid, utilizing two main storage methods: compressed gas storage and cryogenic liquefied storage. High-pressure gaseous CO₂ storage is widely used for short-term buffering, typically at pressures ranging from 50 to 80 bar, depending on process requirements. On the other hand, liquid CO₂ storage is preferred for longer-term storage and transportation, as it significantly reduces volume and allows for efficient handling. However, to store CO₂ in a liquid state, liquefaction is required, involving a series of compression and cooling steps to reach cryogenic temperatures (~ -50°C to -56°C at approximately 6–7 bar).

3.1.3.11 CO₂ TRANSPORT

In case of CO₂ capture and methanol synthesis taking place in different locations, the e-methanol value chain must include CO₂ transportation.

For CO₂ transport, compressed carbon dioxide is stored in high-pressure tanks, typically made from steel or composite materials, ensuring structural integrity and operational safety. In road transport, horizontal cylindrical tanks are preferred due to their stability and ease of handling, while cryogenic tanks are used in maritime transport for liquid CO₂. Although liquefied CO₂ storage significantly

reduces volume, its cryogenic systems require precise insulation and continuous pressure management to prevent losses.

For the purposes of the POSEIDON project, long-distance or maritime CO₂ transport will not be analyzed.

3.1.4 GENERIC VISION OF THE “FEEDSTOCK” VALUE CHAIN

A consolidated version of the feedstock part of the POSEIDON value chain integrating the different technologies mentioned above is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Generic “Feedstock” value chain considered in POSEIDON.

3.1.5 USING CO₂ FROM AN INDUSTRIAL SOURCE – THE CASE STUDY OF THESSALONIKI

POSEIDON’s case study in Thessaloniki is based on CO₂ captured from the local lime production plant (CAO Hellas). The “resources” part of the value chain presented below (Figure 9) is therefore similar to the simplified one and does not need any further explanations.

Figure 9: “Feedstock” value chain applied to an industrial CO₂ emitter.

3.1.6 USING CO₂ FROM A BIOGAS PRODUCTION PLANT – THE CASE STUDY OF VALENCIA

The value chain considered in the case study of Valencia differs from the previous case study as it considers the use of biogenic CO₂ produced by a biogas plant integrated in a wastewater treatment facility. To be complete, the value chain has to integrate all the steps related to the biogas production and treatment since these steps have some impacts (economic, environmental...) on the rest of the value chain. The hydrogen production steps are similar to the ones presented before (Figure 7). The adapted value chain is presented in Figure 9 and specific steps of this value chain are described in the following chapters.

Figure 10: “Feedstock” value chain applied to a biogas plant as CO₂ source.

3.1.6.1 WET BIOMASS AND ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

Anaerobic digestion is a fermentation process that converts wet biomass resources into biogas and digestate. The resources fed into the digester can be (non-exhaustive list):

- Wastewater treatment sludges (case of Valencia);
- Agricultural residues / effluents (manure, crop residues...);
- Energy crops;
- Organic fractions of municipal wastes.
- Industrial organic wastes / effluents.
- ...

Depending on the resources considered the anaerobic digestion process will differ, and the quantity / quality of the produced biogas and digestate will change.

We will therefore consider an anaerobic digestion plant typology compatible with usual types of European plants such as (non-exhaustive list):

- Agricultural biogas plants using mainly manure and agricultural products / residues;
- Municipal waste digestion plants;
- Sewage sludge digestion plants;
- Industrial plants (treating industrial organic wastes / wastewaters);
- Mixed territorial plants fed with a combination of resources;
- ...

3.1.6.2 DIGESTATE MANAGEMENT

The main by-product of anaerobic digestion is a liquid, organic fraction called digestate. Depending on the feedstock used in the anaerobic digestion process, the quality and status of the digestate will differ, which has an impact on its management and associated costs:

- For agricultural anaerobic digestion plants, using exclusively agricultural (by-)products, it is possible to valorize the digestate as fertilizer in the fields.
- For anaerobic digestion plants using waste streams (WWTP sludges, organic fraction of municipal wastes, industrial wastes), the digestate can be considered as a waste and significant costs are incurred for its treatment (drying...) and disposal.

The digestate management rules are not unified at European scale and country specific analysis will need to be done.

3.1.6.3 BIOGAS PURIFICATION

Raw biogas produced by anaerobic digestion plants is mainly composed of methane (40 – 60%) and carbon dioxide (40 – 55%) and contains smaller amounts of other components (e.g. hydrogen sulfur, siloxanes...) that needs to be removed before further biogas use.

The main contaminants that need to be removed from the biogas are:

- Hydrogen sulfate (H_2S): this compound is a poison for most of the catalysts and needs to be removed before any catalytic reaction (like synthetic fuel production).
- Siloxanes: these organic-silicon compounds are problematic for biogas combustion and are systematically removed before valorization.

Depending on the biogas flow and the respective concentrations of the contaminants, different treatment technologies can be considered (activated carbon, chemical reactions...). Once purified, the biogas contains almost exclusively methane and carbon dioxide.

3.1.6.4 BIOGAS UPGRADE

This purified biogas can be upgraded in order to separate the methane and carbon dioxide and different upgrade technologies can be considered (non-exhaustive list):

- Pressure swing adsorption;
- Membrane;
- Cryogenic;
- Physical absorption;
- ...

These technologies produce two main products that can be further valorized:

- Bio-methane
- Biogenic CO_2

3.1.6.5 BIO-METHANE MANAGEMENT

After the upgrading process, produced methane is usually further processed (by odorization, compression...) and injected in the natural gas grid, thus generating incomes for the plant operator.

3.1.6.6 CO₂ PURIFICATION

As introduced in the subchapter dedicated to CO₂ capture from industrial sources (3.1.1.4), an extra purification step of the CO₂ flow coming from the biogas upgrade technology might be needed in order to ensure that no contaminants are present in the gas and that no damage are done to the methanol catalytic synthesis reactor.

3.2 SYNTHETIC METHANOL PRODUCTION

3.2.1 GENERIC CASE OF METHANOL SYNTHESIS

The generic representation of the methanol synthesis of the value chain is represented in Figure 10.

Figure 11: Generic “Methanol synthesis” value chain.

3.2.1.1 METHANOL SYNTHESIS

Methanol production is a catalytic reaction. Different technologies at different TRL level could be envisaged to produce methanol from CO₂ and H₂

- Direct methanolation converting H₂ and CO₂ into methanol;
- Indirect methanolation first converting CO₂ to syngas (mixture of H₂ and CO) through Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) followed by a catalytic synthesis of methanol.

Most of the mature e-methanol synthesis plants currently available operate under conditions close to those of fossil fuel production, with temperatures between 220°C and 280°C and pressures of 50 to 80 bar, using traditional CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃ (CZA) catalysts. Their conversion rate is around 25%, imposed by the thermodynamics at this pressure, which requires multiple loops for higher CO₂/H₂ to methanol conversion rate. The specific case of the ICODOS methanol technology, which will be thoroughly tested in POSEIDON project, is described in chapter 3.2.2.

3.2.1.2 METHANOL / WATER SEPARATION

The chemical reaction leading to the production of methanol produces up to one molecule of water per molecule of methanol. This leads to the production of a water / methanol mixture containing up to 64 wt% of methanol and 36wt% of water. Before any further use, methanol and water need to be separated.

As methanol is soluble in water, this step is usually done by distillation of the mix, producing 2 flows:

- Methanol flow with few percentage of remaining water and possibly few percentage of methanolation process by-products;

- Water flow still containing some methanol and other by-products of methanolation process.

The quality of produced methanol needed (i.e. the percentage of water and other by-products still present in the product) usually depends on its valorization route (fuel for engine, use as chemical component...) and will define the setting of distillation compartment as well as the energy requirement for the process.

3.2.1.3 WASTEWATER MANAGEMENT

The water flow coming from the methanol / water separation unit still contains methanol and some other contaminants. Its treatment might therefore be needed before it's use / release as wastewater.

3.2.1.4 ONSITE METHANOL STORAGE AND CONDITIONING

Depending on the methanol logistics to be considered in the value chain, local storage and conditioning will be needed.

3.2.2 THE SPECIFIC CASE OF THE ICODOS TECHNOLOGY

ICODOS is developing a patented hybrid process for CO₂ capture and conversion into e-methanol not yet available at industrial scale. It integrates the following technological brick which have been introduced before:

- Water electrolysis;
- Separation of the methane and carbon dioxide present in the biogas (biogas upgrade);
- CO₂ purification step (not necessary in ICODOS case);
- Methanol synthesis;
- Methanol / water separation.

The value chain scheme of the ICODOS technology is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 12: ICODOS “Methanol synthesis” Technology.

ICODOS integrated a direct methanolation unit which uses the methanol / water mixture coming from methanol synthesis as CO₂ absorbent in the CO₂ capture compartment of the process. The high pressure H₂ needed for the methanol synthesis is directly injected into the desorption stage to enhance CO₂ desorption. The catalyst used in the methanol synthesis is a commercial CuO/ZnO-based catalyst.

The patented process reduces energy requirement by up to 30% compared to conventional amine-based technology for CO₂ concentrations in off-gas over 5 vol-% and has lower equipment requirements e.g. for compression. In addition, it simplifies the process by reducing the number of units, operates without additional solvent for CO₂ capture and can potentially remove sulfur impurities (H₂S) from the gas such as biogas to be utilized. Additionally, this novel process produces no CO₂ solvent waste as the product of the e-methanol synthesis (e-methanol / water mixture) is being used as CO₂ solvent. The hybrid process also allows the upgrading of biogas to bio-methane for further distribution and use.

The functional scheme of the process is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 13: Functional scheme of the ICODOS technology fed with biogas (Source: ICODOS)

Implementing ICODOS technology into the Valencia use case drastically simplifies the value chain representation. The corresponding value chain is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 14: Valencia Case study integrating ICODOS “Methanol synthesis” Technology.

3.3 SYNTHETIC METHANOL LOGISTICS AND BUNKERING

POSEIDON project will investigate centralized and decentralized methanol production concepts, comparing the advantages and drawbacks of both systems:

- **the “decentralized” concept** tries to maximize the valorization of biogenic CO₂ emissions. These CO₂ sources units are indeed usually quite small (< few MW), distributed over the territory and not directly connected to logistic hubs and methanol consumers (e.g. ports...). This concept consists of a small synthetic methanol production unit on the CO₂ emitter’s site, and the produced fuel is transported to the ports. It takes advantage of the modularity of the ICODOS technology as well as the synergies that can be done with biogas / biomethane production or between onsite hydrogen production and biomass combustion (e.g. valorization of the co-produced O₂ for oxy-combustion). However, the economic impact of the small size of the plants has to be investigated.
 - ⇒ **This concept is investigated in the project through the case study done with Global Omnium and the port of Valencia.**
- **The “centralized” concept** focuses on the valorization of larger CO₂ emissions from industry. These CO₂ sources are usually quite big and centralized making it possible to achieve economies of scale on the CO₂ capture, fuel production and logistic.
 - ⇒ **This concept is investigated in the project through the case study done with CAO Hellas and the port of Thessaloniki.**

Hybrid concepts (mixing centralized and decentralized production) will also be investigated in the replicability study and the deployment strategy as part of WP6 of POSEIDON project.

Figure 15: Logistics of the “e-methanol as fuel for vessels” value chain.

3.3.1 E-METHANOL TRANSPORT

In both concepts introduced in chapter 3.3, transport of e-methanol from the production facility to the port is necessary. Different transport systems can be investigated depending on the distance and the quantity of methanol produced:

- Road transport by trucks;
- Rail transport by trains;
- Transport by pipeline.

In the POSEIDON project, ship transport of methanol will not be considered as we do not analyze international supply chains of methanol.

3.3.2 PORT LOGISTICS AND SHIP BUNKERING

Once arrived at the port, the fuel needs to be stored locally before being fueled to the different vessels. Depending on the type of vessel, different bunkering technologies can be considered:

- “Truck to ship” consists of loading the fuel to the vessel directly from a tanker truck (& trailers) (Figure 15). This bunkering method is adapted to vessels with relatively small fuel requirement. As methanol is a quite recent fuel in the maritime sector, this is currently the most used bunkering method as it does not require big changes in the port infrastructure.

Figure 12: Stena Germanica bunkering methanol from a tanker truck with trailer (photo: J.Ellis)

Figure 16: Methanol truck to ship bunkering (Ellis, et al., 2021)

- “Ship to ship” (or barge to ship) consists of using a barge / tanker to fuel the receiving vessel (Figure 16). This method is used for most of the large vessels, even though it is not yet widely spread for methanol.

Figure 17: Barge to ship methanol bunkering (Ellis, et al., 2021)

- “Pipe to ship” refers to the connection of an onshore storage infrastructure to the receiving vessel (no public picture available).

Thanks to the different workshops held within the POSEIDON project (see chapter 2) as well as several discussions between project partners, we have agreed on the following lists of vessel types that will be considered in future works:

- Tugboat;
- Ferry;
- Cruise vessel;
- Container vessel (e.g. feeder, ...);
- Other 2 stroke vessels (e.g. bulker, small tanker etc.).

3.4 ONBOARD

The last part of the value chain describes what happens “Onboard”, once the fuel has been bunkered on the vessel. This section provides a generic view of the chain that will need to be further detailed for the different types of vessels considered in the project. In fact, each vessel has its specificity, especially regarding how the “hotel load” (i.e. onboard electricity, heat and cold demand) is produced.

Currently almost all the vessels using methanol for propulsion integrate dual fuel engines, running both on Marine Diesel Oil (MDO) and methanol as fuel. Dual fuel engines are equipped with two parallel injection systems for each cylinder (one dedicated to MDO and one dedicated to methanol). This allows the engine to run either 100% on MDO or in dual fuel mode (methanol / MDO).

Due to methanol’s chemical properties (low cetane number leading to ignition issues) the use of pure methanol engines might be problematic. To overcome this issue, MDO can be used as ignition fuel

in order to ensure a good ignition and combustion of the fuel-air mixture³. A min. share of approx. 3 – 5% (based on the energy content) of MDO is usually used during methanol operation.

The flexibility given by dual fuel engines is important for vessel operators as:

- Methanol is not available in every port and the vessel needs to be able to bunker and run on MDO if needed;
- MDO is needed for safe return to the port in case of problem.

This implies that vessels using methanol as fuel needs to have two complete fuel lines including:

- Capacity to bunker the fuel;
- Onboard fuel storage system;
- Onboard fuel preparation / purification system;
- Fuel injection system in the engine.

This is illustrated in Figure 17.

Figure 18: “Onboard” Value chain scheme of the use of synthetic methanol in vessels.

Depending on the vessel type, additional genset(s) (electricity generation systems) might have to be integrated in the value chain. This genset(s) (usually combustion engines) are dedicated to supply the energy needed for the “Hotel Load” of the vessel and can be “standard” engines running on MDO and / or dual fuel engines (as the main propulsion engine). In POSEIDON, the use of methanol fuel cells as gensets to cover all or part of the hotel load of the vessels will also be investigated. This requires an additional step of methanol reforming to produce hydrogen that will be fueled in the fuel cell system.

These different options have to be considered as they have an impact on the effective decarbonation of the vessels using methanol as fuel (Figure 18).

³ High-pressure direct injection of methanol and pilot diesel: a non-premixed dual-fuel engine concept, Y. Dong et al., Fuel 277 (2020) 117932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117932>

Figure 19: Complete “Onboard” Value chain scheme of the use of synthetic methanol in vessels.

4 MAIN STAKEHOLDERS OF THE POSEIDON VALUE CHAIN

4.1 DEFINITION OF THE STAKEHOLDERS’ GROUPS

The following table (Table 3) presents the main target groups of the POSEIDON project which were divided into 8 categories.

The first three target groups (TG1-3) are the key stakeholders of the value chain that will provide feedstocks (energy utilities, biogas plants, hydrogen suppliers), operate the e-methanol plant (plant operators), store and distribute the produced fuel to ships (fuel suppliers; fuel logistic service providers) and users of the e-methanol as fuel (vessel operators). These target groups also include industrial partners that are essential to the operation of the value chain such as component suppliers for the e-methanol plant, engine manufacturers, ship builders. Most of these players have a commercial relationship with each other, with products from some being purchased or transported by others.

The fourth target group (TG4) corresponds to the central players in the implementation and operation of the e-methanol value chain, namely the project developer and the port administration, respectively. They are key for the success of a new e-methanol project and may act as technical and administrative coordinators and as project promoters by uniting all other players around the project. In some cases, their roles can also evolve from the development to the operational phase: they may be responsible for other activities, for example a project developer may become the owner and operator of the fuel plant, and the port authority may extend its activities to fuel supply and logistics.

Table 2: Main stakeholders of the POSEIDON value chain

TG	Target group	Primary interests with regard the value chain to be implemented
TG1	Vessel operator	Comply with legislation, promote own green image, switch to renewable e-fuels available in large quantities which offer similar/better technical/economic performances than fossil ones
	Ship builders including engine manufacturers	Have renewable e-fuel available in sufficient quality and quantity requiring low maintenance and ensuring reliable operation
	Fuel suppliers including companies responsible for fuel logistics	Supply e-fuels with the guarantee of high quality, sufficient quantities and attractive price
TG2	Potential plant operators (companies, port authorities, ...)	Be able to easily deploy and run a power to e-methanol plant with low OPEX/CAPEX and low maintenance and service requirements ensuring short payback time

TG3	Feedstock (CO₂) providers (chemical companies, lime producers, wastewater treatment plant operators, biogas plant operators)	Comply with emissions regulations by reducing the CO ₂ footprint of the own business, and find ways to exploit unwanted emissions or by-products
	Feedstock (H₂) providers	Participate in the industrial deployment synthetic fuel and develop new H ₂ markets.
	Energy utilities and energy companies providing renewable electricity	Support the decarbonisation of hard-to-electrify sectors and the integration of large quantities of renewable sources
TG4	Port operators / authorities and local authorities	Comply with legislation on zero emissions and decarbonisation and build infrastructure for renewable e-fuel bunkering
	Project developers , engineering offices and system integrators	Support the implementation of renewable e-fuel technologies by considering various requirements and selecting the most efficient technologies
TG5	EU research and scientific community	Initiate collaboration with industrial partners to progress SoA, contribute to education of future engineers and maintain EU scientific leadership in renewable e-fuels
TG6	Wider EU e-methanol community including associations, expert and interest groups, similar projects	Support the definition of standards and codes to ensure interoperability of novel technologies and build a community of followers to accelerate the transition towards green e-fuels in shipping
TG7	Policy makers and standardisation/IP bodies	Better understand benefits of renewable e-fuels in terms of HSE and risks and develop and adopt regulations supporting decarbonisation targets and use of renewable e-fuels
TG8	General public / civil society	Broaden knowledge on renewable e-fuels and support initiatives promoting better air quality in harbour cities and low GHG emissions in transport

The other target groups (TG5-8) are a little further away from the project development and operation. However, they play an important role in the success of the e-methanol value chain for shipping. The EU and research community (TG5) is instrumental in developing and demonstrating innovative renewable fuel solutions together with industrial partners and in training young professionals, both activities that are essential for a performant renewable fuel economy. Further stakeholders are the wider e-methanol community (TG6) and policy makers (TG7), that are key for the replication of the POSEIDON concept and the development of a favorable legal framework and standards, guarantying viable business models and the interoperability of the new technologies for fuel

production, distribution and end use. The last stakeholder group (TG8) is the civil society which is more and more impacted by climate change. The POSEIDON project will try to address their concerns and needs since this group can have a decisive supportive role in launching decarbonization initiatives such as the implementation of new value chains based on e-methanol in EU ports.

4.2 RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS AND STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT IN POSEIDON

The following Figure 19 presents the main target groups and their position in the POSEIDON’s value chain. It can be observed that some stakeholders have a clear position in the value chain, while others stretch across several stages of the value chain. The last four groups (TG5-8) are not directly linked to the value chain as such, but rather related to the wider “renewable fuel” ecosystem. Furthermore, this figure illustrates the type of relationships these stakeholders may have: partners located in the value chain (top part of the picture) are more likely to have commercial relationships with each other, while relationships between interest groups 1 to 4 and 5 to 8 (bottom part of the picture) are more oriented towards partnerships.

Figure 20: Position of stakeholders in the POSEIDON value chain.

The involvement of these stakeholders is the key to the successful realization of the whole value chain. In POSEIDON, two local communities of practice (chapter 2.2) gathering local stakeholders from Valencia and Thessaloniki respectively will be established. These COPs will have two main objectives:

1. To strengthen the collaboration between stakeholders and be an open platform for knowledge exchange,
2. To prepare and support the post-project implementation of local value chains by co-developing project outputs and promoting them outside the COPs.

First meetings between project partners and COP members have already taken place. Additional information on COP can be found in chapter 5.1.2 and in deliverable D2.1 on COP framework.

5 POSEIDON VALUE CHAIN RELATED TASKS

Works conducted as part of the task T2.1 resulting in e-methanol as fuel for vessels value chain described in chapter 3 set the ground and boundaries for actions planned in further steps of the POSEIDON project. Figure 20 presents an overview of the most important tasks within WP2 and WP5 that will build upon the POSEIDON value chain. A description of the tasks will be provided in the following sections.

Figure 21: Inter-task data flow based on established e-methanol as fuel for vessels value chain.

5.1 VALUE CHAIN IMPLEMENTATION AND IMPACT ON ANALYSED CASE STUDIES

5.1.1 DECARBONIZATION OF THE MARITIME SECTOR - TARGETS AND CHALLENGES FOR THE STAKEHOLDERS ALONG VALUE CHAIN

As part of **Task 2.2** "Decarbonization of the maritime sector, targets and challenges for the stakeholders; barriers and opportunities for the implementation of e-methanol in vessels", the objective will be to gather and analyze the technical, environmental, and regulatory aspects of the decarbonization of maritime sector, with a special focus on the use of alternative fuels (bio / e-fuels) for the propulsion of vessels. Roadmaps, barriers and constraints will be analyzed, and different fuel options will be compared for defined types of vessels and routes. The identified aspects will be cross checked with each brick of POSEIDON's value chain to identify potential challenges requiring mitigation measures.

The activities within the task T2.2 were kicked-off internally by the task leader RINA Consulting SPA (RINA), and an overview of planned works was presented in March 2024 to all project partners during the consortium meeting (Figure 21).

Figure 22: T2.2 planned activities

The value chain as described in Chapter 3 sets the scope of this activities, giving the global frame of what will need to be analyzed.

5.1.2 FEEDBACK TO BE PROVIDED BY COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE (COP) MEMBERS

The main goal behind establishing Communities Of Practice in the ports of Valencia and Thessaloniki is to bring together local project partners and external networks and stakeholders interested in the decarbonization of the maritime sector and its transition to renewable fuels. The COP members are positioned along the e-methanol value chain and can provide feedback and co-create results together with the project partners.

More specifically, following support is expected to be provided by COP members to WP2 and WP5 tasks:

- T2.2 – Challenges related to shipping decarbonization: COP members can provide feedback on needs and challenges related to the future value chain implementation;
- T2.5 – Value chain scenarios: COP members can help to select the 3 main scenarios to be assessed for each use case;
- T5.4 - Development of value chain modelling tool: COP members can act as beta testers of the modelling tool;
- T5.5 – Summary of scenarios assessment: COP members can support the identification of the most promising scenario and the definition of next steps required for the value chain implementation.

The task will be led by Steinbeis with local coordination from ThPA (Thessaloniki Port Authority) and FVP (Fundación Valencia Port). The developed e-methanol as fuel value chain described in Chapter 3 was presented and discussed with local COP members during the consortium meeting held in Valencia in March 2024. As the following figure shows, a preliminary workplan including COP meetings was already developed. It is planned that two COP meetings will take place every year until project end. Further information can be found in D2.1 on COP framework.

Figure 23: T2.3 Preliminary COP workplan (Steinbeis)

5.1.3 DEFINITION OF THE USECASE SCENARIOS

Two case studies centered around the ports of Thessaloniki and Valencia, will be analyzed within the project’s parameters. To allow thorough investigation for each of the location a detailed description of the conditions needs to be provided.

Based on the POSEIDON “e-methanol as e-fuel for vessels” value chain, 3 separate scenarios will be defined for each of the case study. Work will be conducted by local project partners to make the scenarios as representative as possible of local conditions. The scenarios will be additionally validated by local COP members. These scenarios built upon assumptions will describe the main characteristics of the value chain including parameters such as (non-exhaustive list):

- Source of electricity for hydrogen production and other processes;
- CO₂ source and gas composition;
- Technologies to be considered in different steps of the process (type of electrolyser, CO₂ capture, etc.);
- Feedstock/product logistics;
- Final usage of the product (type of vessel, etc.).

This activity will be conducted as part of the T2.5 “Scenarios of the complete value chains for the case studies and associated datasets”. Data produced will be used in further WP5 tasks. The scope of T2.5 is presented in Figure 23.

Figure 24: T2.5 – Value chain implementation scenarios

5.2 FURTHER USE OF THE VALUE CHAIN IN ASSESMENT ACTIVITIES

WP5’s main focus is the implementation and the assessment of the “e-methanol as e-fuel for vessel” value chain established in WP2. This task will be carried out in close cooperation with both work packages, based on regular exchanges and workshops.

5.2.1 SCOPING OF THE EVALUATION TASKS

As the first step to structure POSEIDON’s data, a database, based on established value chain, is being developed. This database will be the backbone of the whole project, providing homogeneous and coherent data to all the other deliverables in the project, especially those produced in WP2 and WP5. For each technological brick of the value chain, main data (technical, economic, environmental...) will be gathered by the project’s experts and stored, in unified manner, in the database.

To ensure that all necessary information related to the different technological bricks of value chain is identified, the structure of the database and list of data that needs to be stored will be cross-checked by participants of following tasks:

- T5.1 – Techno-economic analysis and life cycle costing;
- T5.2 – Assessment of environmental impacts using LCA;
- T5.3 – Social impacts and acceptance;
- T5.4 – Development of the value chain modelling tool.

All these activities related to the structure of the POSEIDON project database will consolidate the milestone 3 entitled “Final version of methods for techno-economic analysis, environmental and social life cycle assessment” (M#3, M11). It will allow the collection, storage and sharing of information such as feedstock amounts, energy consumption, process-by-products, etc. with all the partners.

Using their experience, expertise and results from past activities as well as literature data, the partners will provide technology description according to their competences as follows (non-exhaustive list):

- CO₂ capture (CERTH, EDF);
- Biogas generation and purification (GOMSL, EIFER);
- H₂ production (EIFER);
- (e-)-methanol synthesis (EIFER, ICODOS);
- Port infrastructure & Bunkering (FVP, ThPA);
- Vessels (FC, Win GD);
- MeOH storage (FC, FVP, ThPA);
- Methanol engines (IFM, WinGD, AUTH, STEMS);
- Onboard MeOH reforming, onboard Fuel cell systems, onboard energy distribution and electrical engines for vessels (FC, EIFER);
- Gas/liquid logistics & storage (FVP, ThPA).

Gathered data will be presented in two deliverables:

- A synthesis report presenting the main technologies, their state of the art and planned evolution (D2.4);
- POSEIDON Project Data Library (D.2.8),

The POSEIDON database together with the defined use case scenarios described in D2.5 will lay the ground for the assessment activities in WP5. The scoping of the evaluation tasks will be prepared within **T2.4** “Libraries of components and technologies” summarized in Figure 24.

Figure 25: T2.4 – Work structure and connecting value chain with WP5.

5.2.1.1 TECHNO-ECONOMIC ASSESMENT

Techno-economic analysis for established e-methanol as e-fuel for vessel value chain will be conducted within task T5.1 with its main goals to:

- Establish the methodology for the Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA) and Life cycle costing (LCC);
- Investigate available technologies to supply e-methanol as marine e-fuel and the associated costs of the defined case studies scenarios;
- Determine the life cycle costs of each scenario, aligned with the system boundaries.

This task will draw data from the following tasks:

- T2.1 – Mapping of the value chain and of the key stakeholders (Chapter 3);
- T2.4 – Libraries of components and technologies (Chapter 5.2.1);
- T2.5 – Scenarios of the complete value chains for the case studies and associated datasets (Chapter 5.1.3),

while, at the same time, providing main KPI's and list of needed data for last two points.

5.2.1.2 LCA ASSESMENT

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for established e-methanol as e-fuel for vessel value chain will be

conducted within task T5.2 with its main goals to:

- Define of the LCA methodologies applied to the value chain;
- Define the structure and the KPIs that will be used in the simulation tool;
- Perform LCA to all of the defined scenarios, according to the described technological characteristics.

This task draw data from the following tasks:

- T2.1 – Mapping of the value chain and of the key stakeholders (Chapter 3);
- T2.4 – Libraries of components and technologies (Chapter 5.2.1);
- T2.5 – Scenarios of the complete value chains for the case studies and associated datasets (Chapter 5.1.3),

while, at the same time, providing main KPI's and list of needed data for last two points.

5.2.1.3 SOCIAL ASSESSMENT

The social impact and acceptance analysis for established e-methanol as e-fuel for vessel value chain will be conducted within task T5.3 with its main goals to:

- Define social impacts and the acceptance of the value chain;
- Define the structure and KPIs that will be used in the simulation tool;
- Perform the social impact assessment (S-LCA) and evaluation of acceptance to all the defined scenarios.

This task will set its methodology along the results from tasks:

- T2.1 – Mapping of the value chain and of the key stakeholders (Chapter 3);
- T2.4 – Libraries of components and technologies (Chapter 5.2.1);
- T2.5 – Scenarios of the complete value chains for the case studies and associated datasets (Chapter 5.1.3),

while, at the same time, providing main KPI's and list of needed data for last two points.

The summary for Assessment activities realized within tasks T5.1-T5.3 is presented in Figure 25.

Figure 26: T5.1-5.3 – Assessment Activities

5.2.2 VALUE CHAIN MODELING TOOL

The KPI's based on established e-methanol as fuel for vessels value chain and defined in tasks T5.1-T5.3 will be furtherly used to define the global structure of the value chain modeling tool (T5.4 – D5.3). This structure will include all the different bricks and calculation steps that will have to be integrated for the simulations.

Every brick and step of created e-methanol as fuel for vessels value chain (Chapter 3) model will be a separate software model developed from the technical specifications. For the modeling tool to be built according to defined needs, each brick needs to be described in a homogeneous way. EIFER, within task 5.4, will develop a Word and an Excel template summarizing main information of each model including:

- Model inputs and outputs definitions:
 - o Data types: Numeric, text, single value, multiple values (time-series), etc.;
- Formulation of model's behavior:
 - o Conversion from inputs to outputs;
 - o Dependencies on other parameters (size...);
- Control variables:
 - o Not inherent features of model's physical behavior but necessary for the value chain operation;
- Range of operation:

- Model’s upper and lower limits of operation;
- Instances:
 - Different variations of a model. For example, technology type (PEM, SOFC).

Final version of list of parameters will mark reaching POSEIDON project milestone #3 (M#3, M11). This milestone will set the detailed boundaries for project database and will be used both in WP2 and WP5 activities. After gathering all needed data in works planned in WP2 the design team will incorporate the technical information into software that will allow users of the tool to compare scenarios and to perform a sensitivity analysis for their use cases. The summary of actions planned regarding modeling tool are presented in Figure 26.

Figure 27: T5.4 – Modeling Tool

6 CONCLUSION

The definition of the value chain considered in the project was necessary to provide a clear framework for future scientific work and a common understanding of the value chain between partners. It is the fruit of collaborative work in the form of workshops involving project partners and external members such as COP and AB members.

It allowed partners to share their ideas and work towards a common view of POSEIDON value chain on the use of alternative fuel in vessels for the decarbonization of the maritime sector. The value chain will be used in many activities such as the value chain modeling tool (T5.4), all the assessment tasks (T5.1-3) and the state of the art / data collection (T2.4). A summary scheme of the links between the different tasks (focus WP2/WP5) is presented in Figure 27.

Figure 28: Links between WP2 / WP5 tasks

The framework of the value chain will potentially evolve along the lifetime of the project according to the results of future POSEIDON activities. Any updates will be documented in the upcoming deliverables within WP2 and WP5.

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